

Global parameter determination in the Astrometric Global Iterative Solution

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ABSTRACT. This note describes the general principle for the determination of global parameters in the Astrometric GIS, using as an example the simple case of two global parameters: a correction to the adopted value of the PPN parameter γ , and a scale correction to the barycentric velocity of Gaia as used for calculating stellar aberration.

1 Introduction

The Astrometric Global Iterative Solution (GIS) aims at the consistent determination of the instrument attitude, instrument calibration, and astrometric parameters by processing a subset of 10 to 100 million primary stars. Optionally this process may include the determination of a certain number of global parameters as well, the most well-known example being the PPN parameter γ expressing the strength of the gravitational deflection of light (with γ equal to 0 in Newtonian theory and 1 in General Relativity). In reality up to several hundred global parameters may eventually be considered.

From a data processing point of view, there is not much difference between global parameters and instrument calibration parameters; indeed, it might be possible and even convenient to regard the global parameters as just another set of calibration parameters. On the other hand, there are also good reasons to treat the global parameters somewhat separated from the rest of the GIS. The main argument is that we generally know the values of these parameters to a very high accuracy, so it is possible to make a very good astrometric solution without actually solving for them. We also know that solving for the global parameters may weaken the solution considerably, and we may only want to do that on an experimental basis, i.e., not as part of the ‘baseline’ astrometric solution.

A typical scenario might be that a baseline astrometric solution is calculated without any global parameters at all, or rather with their values fixed to standard numbers (such as $\gamma = 1$). After convergence of the GIS, we may introduce some global parameters, make a few additional iterations to monitor the behaviour of the solution, then perhaps return to the baseline solution and start another few iterations with a different set of global parameters, and so on. These non-baseline solutions would typically only result in upper limits for the various global parameters, in which case the results of the baseline solution would be adopted. Only under very special circumstances would we actually be prepared to accept one of the non-baseline solutions as the ‘definitive’ result.

With this in mind we should always define global parameters in such a way that their default values, equal to zero, correspond to the baseline solution. By not solving for the globals, we implicitly set them to zero, resulting in the baseline solution. For example, we have a very high confidence in General Relativity, which implies $\gamma = 1$. The global parameter related to the gravitational deflection of light should therefore not be γ itself, but (for example) the parameter g_0 such that

$$\gamma = 1 + g_0 \quad (1)$$

That is, $g_0 = 0$ corresponds to the baseline case of General Relativity.

The purpose of this note is to describe the mechanics for solving an arbitrary number (n) of global parameters g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{n-1} as part of the Astrometric GIS, in a framework similar to what was considered for the source updating in [1] and for the geometric calibration in [2]. The result of the global processing will be an estimate of the vector \mathbf{g} (of length n) and of its covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{g}}$ (of dimension $n \times n$). Additionally, the solution will provide standard statistics such as the total number of observations used (m), the mean down-weighting factor, and the unit weight error (RMS normalised residual), cf. [1].

In order to formulate the solution in matrix algebra it is useful to have $n > 1$, so we need to invent one more ‘reasonable’ global parameter in addition to g_0 in (1). It is proposed to use a parameter g_1 such that

$$\mathbf{v} = (1 + g_1)\mathbf{v}_{\text{ephem}} \quad (2)$$

is the barycentric velocity of Gaia effectively used to calculate stellar aberration. Here, $\mathbf{v}_{\text{ephem}}$ is the barycentric velocity of Gaia returned by the ephemerides. Thus g_1 amounts to a scaling error on this velocity. It should be clear that this parameter is not proposed because of its scientific interest (probably there is none), but only as an example. It is a useful example, though, since g_1 affects *all* observations, in a significant way ($g_1 = 1$ would give errors with an amplitude of 20 arcsec), and it is largely uncorrelated with both g_0 and parallax.

1.1 Observation equations

The same least-squares terminology and conventions are used here as in [2] (see in particular Sect. 2.3 and the Appendix of that note). Thus the AL field angle residual is¹

$$R_\ell \equiv \eta_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \eta_\ell^{\text{calc}} = \eta_n^0 + \Delta\eta_{fnj} + \delta\eta_{nmk} - F_\eta(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (3)$$

where η_n^0 , $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ and $\delta\eta_{nmk}$ represent the current geometric calibration, \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{g} the current astrometric, attitude and global parameters, and $F()$ is a general procedure for computing (η, ζ) at a given time. These residuals, together with the standard errors σ_ℓ and downweighting factors $d(z_\ell)$, form a main input for the global updating. All these quantities have already been calculated in the last inner iteration of the source updating. They are exactly the same quantities as used for the calibration updating [2].

¹In this and subsequent formulae, we suppress the superscript η used in [2] to denote the AL component of the residual. Since the AC component is never used for the global updating, no ambiguity should result.

To calculate an update to \mathbf{g} from the residuals, we also need the partial derivatives of each residual with respect to each of the global parameters.² Clearly,

$$\frac{\partial R_\ell}{\partial \mathbf{g}} = -\frac{\partial F_\eta}{\partial \mathbf{g}}(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (4)$$

With \mathbf{x} denoting the update to the current value of \mathbf{g} , the general form of the linearized observation equation is (cf. (18) in [2])

$$\left(-\frac{\partial R_\ell}{\partial \mathbf{g}}\right)^\top \mathbf{x} \sim R_\ell \quad (\pm\sigma_\ell) \quad (5)$$

or

$$\frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_0} x_0 + \frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_1} x_1 + \cdots + \frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_{n-1}} x_{n-1} \sim R_\ell \quad (\pm\sigma_\ell) \quad (6)$$

where, for simplicity, we use F_ℓ as an abbreviation for $F_\eta(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g})$.

2 Normal equations

The total set of observation equations constitutes an over-determined system of linear equations: the number of observations (m) is much greater than the number of unknowns (n). The standard way to solve an over-determined system is by the least-squares method – or more specifically the weighted (generalized) least-squares method, where in our case the observations are given the weights $d(z_\ell)\sigma_\ell^{-2}$. The normal equations are

$$\mathbf{N}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{h} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{h} are matrices of dimension $n \times n$ and $n \times 1$, respectively, with elements

$$N_{ij} = \sum_\ell \frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_i} \frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_j} \frac{d(z_\ell)}{\sigma_\ell^2}, \quad h_i = \sum_\ell \frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_i} \frac{d(z_\ell)}{\sigma_\ell^2} R_\ell \quad (8)$$

for $i, j = 0 \dots n-1$. The matrices \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{h} , being sums over all the AL observations of primary sources, can be accumulated in whatever order is computationally and logistically convenient. It should also be noted that \mathbf{N} is symmetric, so it is sufficient to accumulate the $n(n+1)/2$ upper-diagonal elements with $0 \leq i \leq j < n$; the part of the matrix below the diagonal ($i > j$) only needs to be filled in after accumulation but before solution.

3 Solution and updating

After having accumulated the normal equations for all the AL observations, the solution, update and covariance are formally given by

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{N}^{-1}\mathbf{h}, \quad \mathbf{g}_{\text{new}} = \mathbf{g}_{\text{old}} + \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{C}_\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{N}^{-1} \quad (9)$$

It is recommended that the SVD algorithm (see [1]) is used to compute the inverse normal equations matrix. The SVD estimates the rank of \mathbf{N} and provides the pseudo-inverse in case the rank is less than n .

²Note that \mathbf{g} and $\partial R_\ell/\partial \mathbf{g}$ are both vectors (column matrices) of length n .

4 Calculation of partial derivatives

It remains to provide a prescription for calculating $\partial F_\ell / \partial g_i$. Every time a new global parameter is introduced, it will be necessary to provide such a description. However, part of that computation is common to all global parameters, namely the last step transforming from celestial coordinates to the field angles. Thus, what is normally needed is a prescription for calculating $\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial g_i$, where \mathbf{u} is the unit vector representing the proper direction towards the source at the moment of observation. The final step of the transformation is

$$\frac{\partial F_\ell}{\partial g_i} = \sec \zeta_\ell \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \phi_\ell & \cos \phi_\ell & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}(t_\ell) \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial g_i} \quad (10)$$

where $\phi_\ell = \eta_\ell \pm \gamma/2$ (with upper/lower sign for preceding/following field)³ and \mathbf{A} is the attitude matrix.

Specifically, for the proposed two global parameters,

- $\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial g_0 = \partial \mathbf{u} / \partial \gamma$ according to (1), with $\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial \gamma$ explicitly calculated as part of the standard Fundamental Algorithms package;
- for g_1 according to (2) we can use the first-order (classical) aberration formula to derive

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial g_1} = [\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v})] c^{-1} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the barycentric velocity of Gaia (from the ephemerides) and c the speed of light.

In practice, the partial derivatives change so slowly that they only need to be calculated once per FOV transit. The same values can then be used for all the AF observations in a transit. This should be taken advantage of when accumulating the normals in (8). On the other hand it can be noted that the 1×3 matrix pre-multiplying $\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial g_i$ in (10) is the same for all the global parameters in a given FOV transit.

5 Solution statistics

The calculation of various statistics of the solution requires the accumulation of a few additional quantities. Following similar principles as for the source updating [1] we need:

- the total number of observations,

$$m = \sum_{\ell} 1 \quad (12)$$

- the total weight reduction,

$$D = \sum_{\ell} d(z_\ell) \quad (13)$$

³Note that γ here denotes the basic angle.

- and the weighted sum of squared pre-fit residuals,

$$S = \sum_{\ell} \frac{d(z_{\ell})}{\sigma_{\ell}^2} R_{\ell}^2 \quad (14)$$

The computed statistics are the mean weight reduction factor

$$d_{\text{ave}} = D/m \quad (15)$$

and the unit weight error

$$u = 1.03125 \times \sqrt{\frac{S - \mathbf{h}^T \mathbf{x}}{D - n}} \quad (16)$$

Ideally, they should both be close to 1.

References

- [1] Lindegren L., 2004: *A proposed new algorithm for Source Updating*, GAIA-LL-055, Version 1 (12 September 2004)
- [2] Lindegren L., 2005: *Geometric calibration model for the 1M Astrometric GIS demonstration*, GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-063-1 (7 November 2005)

Acronyms

The following table has been generated from the on-line Gaia acronym list:

Acronym	Description
AC	ACross scan (direction)
AF	Astrometric Field (in Astro)
AL	ALong scan (direction)
FOV	Field of View (also denoted FOV)
GIS	(Astrometric) Global Iterative Solution
PPN	Parametrised Post-Newtonian (formalism in General Relativity)
RMS	Root-Mean-Square
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition